

Chemical Physics with Quistors[†]

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A brief review of the present status of applications of Quistors to mass spectrometry, study of ion-molecule reactions, precision hyperfine spectroscopy and molecular ion spectroscopy is presented.

THE objective of this review is to present briefly the current status of applications of the Quistor (Quadrupole Ion Store or Radiofrequency Ion Trap) in the area of chemical physics.

Principle of operation of the device: While the two-dimensional quadrupole mass filter uses four rods of hyperbolic cross section, and with a field diameter $2r_0$, opposite electrodes shorted together, a voltage of $U + V \cos \omega t$ applied across the adjacent electrodes the single particle ion motion is given by the following two Mathieu equations,

$$\frac{d^2x}{d\zeta^2} + (a + 2q \cos 2\zeta) x = 0$$

$$\frac{d^2y}{d\zeta^2} - (a + 2q \cos 2\zeta) y = 0$$

where, $a = \frac{8eU}{mr_0^2\omega^2}$, $q = \frac{4eV}{mr_0^2\omega^2}$, and $\zeta = \frac{\omega t}{2}$.

The radiofrequency ion trap structure (Fig. 1) involves a three-dimensional force field, generated by a voltage $U - V \cos \omega t$ applied between an

Fig. 1. Quadrupole radiofrequency ion trap (Quistor).

annular ring electrode with hyperbolic profile and oriented along the xy plane, and two end-cap electrodes that are hyperboloids of revolution about the z -axis. The ion motion in the latter case is expressed by the following Mathieu equations,

$$\frac{d^2z}{d\zeta^2} + (a_z - 2q_z \cos 2\zeta) z = 0$$

$$\frac{d^2r}{d\zeta^2} + (a_r - 2q_r \cos 2\zeta) r = 0$$

where, $a_z = -2a_r = -\frac{4eU}{mz_0^2\omega^2}$, $q_z = 2q_r = -\frac{2eV}{mz_0^2\omega^2}$,

$\zeta = \frac{\omega t}{2}$, $r_0^2 = 2z_0^2$ and r represents either x or y .

Mathieu equations have stable or unstable solutions depending on the values of the parameters a and q ; the aq plane, therefore, is divided into stable and unstable zones. Unlike the two-dimensional quadrupole, the stability diagram for the quistor is asymmetric with respect to the q -axis (dashed line in Fig. 2; the enclosed region is the stable zone), and usually the lower part of the diagram is used. For a mass selective operation, the voltages applied are such that only a small range of $\Delta m/z$ ions is stable. While the stable condition in a two-dimensional quadrupole means that the ion is confined along the x - and y -direction and it moves with constant velocity along the z -direction, in the three-dimensional force field, a stable motion along the x -, y -, and z -directions means that the ion is 'trapped' inside the structure. The dashed line of Fig. 2 is the theoretical stability diagram corresponding to the single particle ion motion. The solid lines represent experimentally obtained⁵ stability diagrams for various m/z ions and probably include space charge effects. Principles and early applications have been reviewed in detail in Refs. 1 and 2; several aspects of recent applications are presented in Refs. 3 and 4.*

Mass spectrometry: The first obvious application has been to mass spectrometry where it could serve as both a sensitive and a miniature mass spectrometer. In the method of resonance detection¹, besides the rf voltage $V \cos \omega t$, an additional ω_{ac} is applied between the end-cap electrodes. When the stored ions have their fundamental

* This review considers only the rf trap (Quistor) which has also been called the Paul trap (after the inventors of the device, W. Paul and coworkers). The 'Penning traps' have the Quistor structure but for ion confinement, use, instead of the rf field, an electric potential and a magnetic field. Using special ion cooling techniques, nearly Doppler-free spectroscopy has been possible using this device (for example, Ref. 4). A couple of other recent achievements using such traps are, determination of positron/electron g -factor ratio of high accuracy, and a measurement of positron/electron mass ratio which is at least two orders of magnitude more accurate than any previous data (P. B. SCHWINBERG, R. S. VAN DYCK, JR. and H. G. DEHMELT, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1981, 47, 1679; P. B. SCHWINBERG, R. S. VAN DYCK, JR. and H. G. DEHMELT, *Phys. Lett.*, A, 1981, 81, 119).

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Fig. 2. Stability diagrams of the Quistor. The dashed line represents the single particle theoretical stability diagram. The solid lines represent mass dependent stability diagrams obtained from experiments⁶. Areas enclosed by the lines represent the stable zones for ions.

frequency of motion ω_z in the axial direction same as ω_{θ} , ions are collected at the end-cap electrodes, and this current could be detected. In another method⁶ that is commonly used, the quistor is set for a specific m/z and the ion concentration is allowed to build. After an adequate build-up, the ions are pulsed out of the trap to a detector through an aperture on one of the end-caps. In a recent application⁷ using a mass selective instability mode, the trapping voltage applied is such that initially a range of m/z ions are stable and all of them are trapped. The U(dc) or the V cos ωt (rf) voltages are then scanned in a manner such that successively different m/z ions become unstable, they pass out through the field structure, and are detected, leading to a mass spectrum. Using this mode of operation at high background pressures of about 10^{-8} torr of helium or hydrogen—the external gases damping the ion motion—significantly enhanced mass resolution, sensitivity and detection limit have been obtained.

Study of ion-molecule reactions: Ion-molecule reactions have been studied by employing quistors. In the quistor-quadrupole combination instruments⁸ the quistor is used in place of the conventional ion source with the quadrupole acting as the ion detector. In pulsed operation of such experiments, the first pulse results electron impact ionisation of the parent gas inside the confinement region and generates the primary reactant ion. Between two such consecutive ion creation pulses, ion-molecule reactions take place. The ions of interest, primary or secondary, are selectively confined in the trap, and after a variable time period ejected into the

quadrupole and detected. Results are consistent with other techniques, and indicate ion kinetic energy in the range 1-3 eV. Recently ionic multi-photon dissociation processes have been studied⁹ by using quistors, and reaction pathways have been examined by selective removal of possible precursors.

Microwave spectroscopy and atomic hyperfine structure: In the late sixties Schuessler and co-workers¹⁰ first applied the quistor to the study of hyperfine structure of $^3\text{He}^+$ by an exchange collision technique. In this interesting experiment, $^3\text{He}^+$ ions are first generated by electron impact and kept trapped in the confinement region. A beam of spin polarised Cs atoms is then passed through the $^3\text{He}^+$ ion cloud. The polarised Cs beam acts in two ways. First, by spin exchange, it transfers its polarisation to the stored $^3\text{He}^+$ ions itself losing polarisation,

In a simultaneous second process, charge exchange with He^+ takes place. This charge exchange process proceeds through two different channels, the fast singlet channel,

and the slow triplet channels,

ΔE_1 and ΔE_3 are respectively the ionisation energy differences for the singlet and triplet charge-exchange reactions.

The charge-exchange cross section depends on the energy defect ΔE , relative velocity of Cs and He^+ , and the ionisation energies of the ground state Cs and excited He^* atoms. In the case of Cs and He, $\Delta E_1 = 0.08$ eV and $\Delta E_2 = -0.26$ eV, and the singlet charge-exchange cross section is estimated to be about 20 times larger than that of the triplet state. The spin-exchange cross section is much faster than even the singlet charge-exchange cross section; so the trapped ions assume the same polarisation as the Cs atoms in a time interval that is short compared to the neutralisation time. The quistor remains immersed in a magnetic field for the purpose of the microwave spectroscopic experiment. In the third step, when the microwave radiation of the right frequency is shone, the optical transition, $\text{He}^+ \uparrow \rightarrow \text{He}^+ \downarrow$ takes place. When this transition occurs, additional $\text{He}^+ \downarrow$ ions are generated but they lose their charge fast by the singlet channel and hence are lost rapidly from the trap. So if the number of helium ions stored in the trap is monitored as the microwave frequency is swept, the precise frequency of transition is recorded by a rapid loss of ions from the trap. All possible hfs structure of $^3\text{He}^+$ were measured by Schuessler and coworkers using the ion-storage exchange collision technique. This study has been followed by hfs determination of $^{199}\text{Hg}^+$ by other workers¹¹⁻¹⁵ using the ion trap.

A recent application of microwave spectroscopy has been to the determination of ground state hyperfine splitting of $^{137}\text{Ba}^+$ by using tunable lasers¹⁴. The use of tunable lasers opens up more general applications in the spectroscopy of stored ions; it also has the advantage of improved signal to noise ratio. In this particular experiment, schematically shown in Fig. 3, the $6S_{1/2}$ state ($F=2$) ions created by surface ionisation are pumped by a pulsed tunable laser at 493.4 nm. The excited P state has a decay mode to the $5D_{3/2}$ state with a branching ratio of 2.8 and a fluorescence wavelength 649.6 nm. As the microwave output frequency is swept across the hyperfine transition, the fluorescence count rate at 649.6 nm records the occurrence of the hyperfine transition. By application of this method the ground state hyperfine splitting of $^{137}\text{Ba}^+$ has been measured with a precision of 4.6×10^{-11} .

Experiments are underway for storing low energy highly charged ions and also radioactive ions, produced on-line from a nuclear accelerator, for the purpose of atomic spectroscopy¹⁶.

Molecular spectroscopy: Laser induced fluorescence spectra of molecular ions is another area where rf ion traps have been employed.

In the study of fluorescence spectra of BrCN^+ ions¹⁶, the ion trap used was of cylindrical geometry, a variant of the quistor using hyperbolic geometry. In this experiment, the ions are first created by pulsed electron beam bombardment of the parent neutral gas. Any excited electronic states that are created then relax radiatively, and mass selection in the trap takes place. Following

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram showing the transitions involved in ground state hfs determination of $^{137}\text{Ba}^+$ using the Quistor and laser fluorescence¹⁴.

this delay, a 10 ns 1 cm^{-1} bandwidth laser pulse—dye laser pumped by a nitrogen laser—passes through the ion cloud, and any subsequent fluorescence is then monitored at right angles to the exciting radiation. By varying the dye laser frequency the entire spectrum is obtained. Besides other information, the C-Br stretching frequencies of the molecular ion have been derived using this technique.

In another experiment, by monitoring laser induced fluorescence spectra, charge transfer reactions of N_2^+ with Ar and that with N_2 have been studied¹⁷. Ion-molecule reactions alter the internal energy distribution of the trapped N_2^+ ; by monitoring these changes charge transfer cross sections for individual initial vibrational states have been estimated.

Yet in another study¹⁸, radiative lifetimes of excited electronic states of molecular ions have been measured using the ion trap. The storage times used were such that allowed only electronic relaxation. In this experiment, ions which are in the ground electronic state, or in an optically metastable state, are excited with a laser pulse, and the time dependence of the resulting fluorescence is monitored; from this the radiative lifetimes of the upper states could be determined. These studies have included the $\text{N}_2^+ \text{B}^2\Sigma_u^+$ state, $\text{CO}^+ \text{A}^2\Pi$ state, and for the ions CH^+ and CD^+ , obtained from fragmentation of CH_4 , the $\text{A}^1\Pi$ state.

Ion stabilities from theory: The involvement of our laboratory in this area has been in theoretical

Fig. 4. Theoretical stability diagrams from a many-particle calculation showing mass dependence.

examination of the quistor operation; this includes exploring ways by which an external injection could be effected for ions which could not be generated inside the trap, and attempting theoretical prediction of stability properties that takes into account space charge effects. Early work on ion stability properties from theory, is presented in Ref. 2. We first examined¹⁹ ion path lengths which would have influence on overall collision probability. We then initiated a study²⁰ of asymptotic (Fig. 1) pulsed injection of ions. This was examined by Todd and coworkers²¹ using the phase space dynamics method. Later this was extensively studied by O and Schuessler²² which included other injection modes, such as ring injection. We then initiated *ab initio* studies of many-particle systems in an attempt to evolve stability diagrams that include space charge effects. We first examined²³ a conical injection mode around the z-axis and a concentric ring injection; both of these, difficult to execute experimentally, though pertained to many-particle systems, reduced to single particle calculations because of special geometries. Recently, we have made calculations²⁴ on realistic modes using only a few particles but considering all electrostatic and electromagnetic forces besides the Mathieu forces. In the initial study it predicted correctly the nature of shifts of two stability lines. In a recent study²⁵, assuming thermalisation of ions, it has qualitatively predicted correctly the mass dependence (Fig. 4) as observed in experiments⁵ (Fig. 1).

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